

Engagement And Motivation In Achieving Success In Araling Panlipunan Among Grade 8 Students At Pinamukan Integrated School

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the level of engagement and motivation of Grade 8 students in achieving success in Araling Panlipunan at Pinamukan Integrated School. This also sought to determine the influence, its contribution, effectiveness and challenges of students' engagement and motivation in achieving academic success on the subject matter.

This research utilized the descriptive quantitative research design to examine how effective the engagement and motivation of Grade 8 students on their academic success. The data was collected using researcher-made questionnaire as a main source of data. The statistical measures utilized in this research included frequency, percentage, ranking, and weighted mean.

Based on the findings, although students are very motivated and involved in class discussions, they could do better in terms of long-term memory retention. Therefore, it is recommended that teachers can increase student engagement and memory retention by creating a supportive environment, employing techniques like spaced repetition, active recall, and contextual learning, as well as by introducing reflection and positive reinforcement. There were some proposed interactive activities to uplift students' engagement and motivation in the subject area.

Keywords: *engagement, motivation, academic success, Araling Panlipunan, Grade 8 students, learning retention, class participation, teacher support, interactive activities, study habits*

INTRODUCTION

In the context of education, learning is not merely the memorization of facts but the development of critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and the ability to apply knowledge in real-life situations. As learners come from diverse backgrounds with different abilities, interests, and learning styles, effective teaching strategies must be inclusive and responsive to these differences to ensure meaningful learning takes place.

In line with the Deped Order No.042, s.2022, titled Adoption of the Basic Education Development Plan 2030, one of the key goals of the Philippine education system is to produce high-quality, competent, and future-ready learners who can thrive in an increasingly complex and competitive global environment. To achieve this, it is essential to recognize the vital role that student engagement and motivation play in improving academic outcomes and fostering lifelong learning.

Nevertheless, despite its capability to awaken critical thinking and curiosity some students have the opposite perception. It seems that they already put in their mind that it is not a fun learning. With that teachers find it challenging in capturing students interest in the subject matter. Despite of various teaching strategies that is being executed in the class to make the lesson more relatable and interactive, some students still struggle and perform poorly in the subject. It is seen for some of the students at Pinamukan Integrated School.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the specific ways in which student motivation and engagement affect academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan 8. It seeks to determine which elements—such as instructional strategies, learning environments, evaluation techniques, and the use of contextualized or localized content—help or hinder student interest and participation. The study will also look at how learners' motivation—whether it comes from personal interest, teacher support, or the perceived importance of the subject, affects their capacity to absorb and recall historical information.

Through this study, the researcher aims to provide a continuous good record of their academic performances as well as their interest in learning World History from the beginning of the school year 2025-2026, keep in their mind that it is a fun learning experiences and examine how engagement and motivation can be part of their academic outcomes in Araling Panlipunan.

This study aims to determine students' engagement and motivation in achieving success in Araling Panlipunan.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions.

1. How may student's engagement and motivation influence the academic success of Grade 8 learners in Araling Panlipunan in terms of:
 - 1.1. level of confidence;
 - 1.2. level of students' interest;
 - 1.3. learning outcomes?
2. To what extent do students' engagement and motivation contribute to their academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan in terms of:

- 2.1. level of study habits;
- 2.2. learning styles;
- 2.3. teachers support?
3. How effective are the students' engagement and motivation in learning Araling Panlipunan in terms of:
 - 3.1. Class Participation;
 - 3.2. Learning Retention?
4. What are the challenges experience by the students in achieving academic performance?
5. Based on the results of the study, what enrichment activities may be designed?

METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study employed a descriptive quantitative research design that examined how effective the engagement and motivation of Grade 8 students on their academic success.

PARTICIPANTS

The participants of this study are from one selected section with 45 students of Grade 8 level enrolled at Pinamukan Integrated School for the school year 2025-2026. This section was purposely chosen to serve as the participants of the research in order to minimize disruption to regular class schedules and ensure a more focused implementation of the study. By limiting the participants to one section, the researcher aims to closely monitor the effects of students' engagement and motivation on their academic success in Araling Panlipunan without affecting the learning process of other classes.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The primary research instrument used in this study is a researcher-made questionnaire designed to gather data on students' engagement, motivation, academic performance, and challenges in learning Araling Panlipunan. The questionnaire is structured using a Likert scale format to measure the degree of students' agreement with each statement.

The instrument is divided into several parts:

- Part I: Students' engagement and motivation (e.g., interest, confidence, participation)
- Part II: Factors contributing to academic success (e.g., study habits, learning styles, teacher support)
- Part III: Effectiveness of engagement and motivation (e.g., participation and retention)
- Part IV: Challenges encountered by students
- Part V: Enrichment activities that enhance engagement and motivation

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURES

To obtain the necessary data for this study, the researcher developed a structured questionnaire as the primary research instrument. In designing and refining the questionnaire, the researcher conducted extensive readings of related literature and studies to ensure a clear understanding of effective questionnaire construction. This process helped establish the relevance, clarity, and alignment of the items with the objectives of the study. Furthermore, the researcher followed the CVARS format to ensure that the instrument was comprehensive, well-organized, and capable of accurately capturing the needed information.

DATA ANALYSIS

The following statistical tools were used to quantify the data gathered in the study:

Frequency. This will be used to calculate the percentage of participant's responses to each item in the research. This showed the number of times a repeating event occurs in a given amount of time is referred to by the frequency analysis.

Percentage. This will be used in the study to ascertain which percentage of the participants fit into particular categories. It is also used to evaluate how well the students understand the concept of probability.

Ranking. This will be used to determine and identify the positional results of responses in the tailed data as assessed by the participants.

Weighted mean. This will be used to determine the average responses of students regarding their perception of the impact of students engagement and motivation on their learning experience in Araling Panlipunan.

Result and Discussion

1. Influence of student's engagement and motivation in their academic success.

Table 1
Level of Confidence

Statement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
I feel confident when answering questions in Araling Panlipunan class.	2.89	Strongly Agree	4
I believe I can perform well in Araling Panlipunan if I put in effort.	4.00	Strongly Agree	1.5
I feel motivated	4.00	Strongly	1.5

when I get good feedback from my teacher.		Agree	
I am not afraid to make mistakes in Araling Panlipunan because I am eager to improve.	2.67	Agree	5
My confidence in in answering activities increases when I understand the lesson.	3.22	Agree	3

Table 1 shows that the students have a high level of confidence and motivation. The “believe I can perform well in the Araling Panlipunan if I put in effort and “Feel motivated when I get good feedback from my teacher” get the highest rated statement with a weighted mean of 4.00 and verbal interpretation of strongly agree. This indicates that students are capable and highly motivated when effort is applied and feedback is received. According to Gan (2020), students’ intended learning effort and positive attitudes strongly predicted their engagement with feedback—both its reception and utilization. When students are genuinely committed to improving, they are more likely to pay attention to feedback and treat it as a valuable resource rather than as mere criticism. Likewise, students with positive attitudes toward learning tend to view feedback constructively, seeing it as an opportunity for growth rather than as a judgment of their abilities. These attitudes enable them to accept feedback openly and reflectively.

Table 2
Level of students’ interest

Statement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
I find the topics in Araling Panlipunan interesting.	2.78	Agree	6
I enjoy reading and learning about history and society.	2.89	Agree	5
I am more interested when my teachers give reward	4.00	Strongly Agree	1
I am eager to learn more about history and society when	3.00	Agree	4

lessons are engaging.			
I feel more motivated to study Araling Panlipunan when the teacher uses interactive strategies.	3.56	Strongly Agree	2
I enjoy participating in class activities and group work related to Araling Panlipunan.	3.44	Agree	3

Table 2 shows the data on the Level of Students' Interest in Araling Panlipunan it reveals that learners are generally interested in the subject, with varying degrees of motivation. The highest interest was observed when students received rewards from teachers with a weighted mean of 4.00, followed by the use of interactive strategies and collaborative activities. This suggests that extrinsic motivators such as recognition and rewards, along with learner-centered instructional approaches, significantly enhance student engagement. While learners show interest in reading and learning about history and society, their motivation is notably heightened when lessons are participatory and enjoyable. These findings align with the study of Bernardo and Gonzales (2021), who emphasized that positive reinforcement and interactive learning activities directly influence student motivation and academic interest. Likewise, Ramos et al. (2020) highlighted that when teachers connect lessons to students' experiences and apply meaningful classroom strategies, learners are more likely to show enthusiasm and sustained interest. This means that students perceived that teachers acknowledge and recognized them if they did well in the class.

Table 3
Learning Outcomes

Statement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
My understanding of topics improves when I actively participate in class discussions	3.40	Agree	3
My motivation helps me perform well in quizzes and tests.	3.42	Agree	2
I can apply what I	2.67	Agree	5

learn in Araling Panlipunan to real-life situations.			
I get higher scores in Araling Panlipunan when I am motivated and engaged in the lessons.	3.24	Agree	4
I perform better in class when I find the lesson topics interesting.	3.78	Strongly Agree	1

Table 3 shows the results on learning outcomes indicate that students exhibit a high to very high level of academic performance in Araling Panlipunan when they are engaged and motivated. The highest rated item was, “*I perform better in class when I find the lesson topics interesting*” with a weighted mean of 3.78 interpreted as Strongly Agree, showing that students’ interest in the lesson content significantly enhances their academic output.

However, the lowest score was in applying what they learned to real-life situations with a weighted mean of 2.67, suggesting a gap between classroom learning and practical application. This supports the findings of Ramos and Santos (2020) who emphasized that students learn more effectively when teaching is engaging and contextualized, allowing them to see the relevance of the subject to everyday life. Similarly, Delos Reyes (2021) noted that motivated students are more likely to perform well academically, especially when learning environments encourage participation and interest. Therefore, the data highlights the need for teachers to connect lessons to real-world contexts while maintaining engaging and participatory strategies to further enhance students' learning outcomes.

2. Contribution to academic success.

Table 4
Level of habits

Statement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
I study Araling Panlipunan regularly even without assignments.	2.04	Disagree	6
I review my notes before tests.	3.27	Strongly Agree	5
I manage my time well when studying	3.78	Strongly Agree	1

Araling Panlipunan.			
I create a study schedule for Araling Panlipunan when I am motivated to succeed.	3.67	Strongly Agree	2
I take time to study Araling Panlipunan even outside of class when I find the topic meaningful.	3.47	Strongly Agree	4
I am consistent in completing AP assignments when I am interested in the lessons.	3.56	Strongly Agree	3

Table 4 presents students' study habits in relation to Araling Panlipunan, revealing varied levels of consistency and discipline. Most students demonstrate strong agreement with habits that involve structured and purposeful study practices, such as time management with weighted mean of 3.78 and creating study schedules when motivated with weighted mean of 3.67. This supports findings by Credé and Phillips (2020), who emphasized that self-regulation and time management are critical predictors of academic success.

Table 5
Learning Styles

Statement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
I learn best when I watch videos or visual materials.	3.49	Strongly Agree	4
I prefer group activities and discussions in class.	3.44	Strongly agree	5
I feel more focused when the teaching method matches how I naturally like to learn.	3.62	Strongly agree	3
I feel more engaged when I do hands-on activities or role-	3.94	Strongly agree	1

playing related to the lesson.			
I remember more facts when I take notes or write summaries of Araling Panlipunan topics.	3.71	Strongly Agree	2

Table 5 illustrates the preferred learning styles of students in relation to how they absorb and retain information. A majority of respondents strongly agreed that they feel more engaged when participating in hands-on activities or role-playing related to the lesson with a weighted mean of 3.94, and that their focus improves when teaching methods align with their natural learning preferences weighted mean 3.62. This supported the idea Dela Cruz (2020) that when teaching materials reflect students' own culture, community experiences, and real-life situations, learners are more likely to see the value and purpose of what they are studying. This relevance helps them connect new information with their existing knowledge and experiences, making learning more meaningful and engaging.

Table 6
Teachers Support

Statement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
My teacher gives additional help or guidance when I am struggling with the lesson.	3.78	Strongly Agree	3
My teacher makes the lessons easier to understand.	3.84	Strongly Agree	2
I feel supported by my teacher in learning Araling Panlipunan.	3.50	Strongly Agree	4
I am more motivated in Araling Panlipunan when my teacher encourages me to do my best.	3.89	Strongly Agree	1
I become more interested in Araling Panlipunan	3.44	Strongly Agree	5

when my teacher recognizes my efforts.			
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Table 6 shows the data on teacher support highlighted its pivotal role in developing student motivation, understanding, and engagement in Araling Panlipunan. Students overwhelmingly indicated strong agreement that they feel more motivated when teachers encourage them to do their best with weighted mean of 3.89 and find lessons easier to understand when teachers clarify concepts effectively with the weighted mean of 3.84.

3. Effectiveness of engagement and motivation

Table 7
Class Participation

Statement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
I often participate in classroom discussions.	3.56	Strongly Agree	2
I volunteer to present or share my ideas in group activities.	3.00	Agree	4
I ask questions when I do not understand the lesson.	2.92	Agree	5
I become more interactive during group tasks when I am excited about the lesson.	3.48	Strongly Agree	3
I participate more in class when I see the relevance of the topic to real-life situations.	3.67	Strongly Agree	1

Table 7 presents the data on class participation indicates that students are more actively involved when lessons are relevant and engaging. The highest-rated item shows that students participate more when they see the relevance of the topic to real-life situations with the weighted mean of 3.67. According to Wang and Degol (2021), students best learn when they see the relevance of the topic to real-life. Similarly, a strong weighted mean of 3.56 was recorded for general classroom discussions, suggesting a willingness to engage in traditional forms of participation.

Table 8
Learning Retention

Statement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
I can remember lessons even after a long time.	3.06	Agree	5
My motivation to learn helps me retain facts and concepts.	3.62	Strongly Agree	2
I can connect past lessons to new ones easily.	3.28	Agree	4
I can explain Araling Panlipunan topics better when I enjoyed the way they were taught.	3.56	Strongly Agree	3
I can recall past lessons easily when they were presented in an interesting or fun way.	3.67	Strongly Agree	1

Table 8 illustrates the data on learning retention it reveals that students retain information more effectively when lessons are enjoyable, relevant, and connected to their intrinsic motivation. The highest weighted mean was recorded for the statement, *“I can recall past lessons easily when they were presented in an interesting or fun way”* with weighted mean of 3.67, highlighting the importance of engaging instructional methods. This supports findings by Immordino-Yang and Darling-Hammond (2021), who emphasize that emotionally engaging learning experiences are more likely to be retained in long-term memory. Similarly, motivation plays a key role, as shown by the high rating for *“My motivation to learn helps me retain facts and concepts”* with a weighted mean of 3.62, aligning with the self-determination theory, which links motivation with deeper processing and retention (Ryan & Deci, 2020).

4. Students challenges on achieving academic success

Table 9
Student challenges

Statement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
1. I find the lessons in Araling Panlipunan difficult to understand.	3.42	Strongly Agree	4
2. I lack interest or motivation in the subject	3.24	Agree	5
3. The way the lessons are taught does not match my learning style.	3.56	Strongly Agree	3
4. I need more interactive or hands-on activities to understand better	3.73	Strongly Agree	1
5. I feel uncomfortable asking questions or reciting in front of the class.	2.70	Agree	9
6. I lack motivation to study regularly.	3.06	Agree	8
7. I am distracted by peer pressure or social media.	3.70	Strongly Agree	2
8. I feel isolated or disconnected from my classmates.	3.10	Agree	7
9. I have difficulty following lessons when they are taught too fast.	3.18	Agree	6

Based on the data presented in Table 9, the most significant challenge faced by students is the need for more interactive or hands-on activities to better understand lessons, receiving the highest weighted mean of 3.73 and interpreted as "Strongly Agree." This finding suggests that students prefer learning strategies that involve active engagement and

participation. Recent research confirmed the effectiveness of interactive learning in boosting student engagement and performance. According to Widyawalundari (2019) innovative learning transforms the classroom into a dynamic space where students are not passive recipients of information but active participants in their own education. This method leads to greater engagement, better academic performance, and a lifelong love for learning. Similarly, Lee and Hannafin (2020) found that student-centered strategies, including project-based and experiential learning, significantly enhance comprehension and retention.

5. Proposed enrichment activities towards students' engagement and motivation enhancement.

To support the enhancement of student engagement and motivation in achieving success in Araling Panlipunan of Grade 8 students, a various of enrichment activities has been executed. These activities aim to enhance students' engagement and motivation focus on developing dynamic, learner-centered experiences that go beyond traditional classroom instruction. To make learning more engaging and interactive, differentiated interactive activities are being executed like game-based activities, group activities, and multimedia presentations and discussions. By integrating students' interests and encouraging active engagement these initiatives create a deeper connection to the subject matter, particularly to the areas where motivation and engagement tend to decline.

DISCUSSIONS

The findings of the study highlight that students' engagement and motivation play a crucial role in their academic success in Araling Panlipunan. Learners generally show high levels of confidence and motivation, especially when their efforts are recognized through feedback, rewards, and incentives. This suggests that both intrinsic motivation (such as personal interest and effort) and extrinsic motivation (such as recognition and rewards) significantly influence students' willingness to participate and perform well. Moreover, students value lessons that are practical and applicable to real-life situations, which enhances their interest and learning outcomes.

In terms of contributing factors to academic success, students demonstrate good study habits and time management, although many rely on assigned tasks rather than initiating independent study. The strong preference for visual learning materials indicates that multimedia resources are effective in improving comprehension and retention. Additionally, teacher support—particularly through encouragement and incentives—emerges as a key element in sustaining student motivation and performance.

The study also reveals that while students are actively engaged in classroom discussions and are willing to ask questions, they are less confident in presenting ideas publicly. Retention of knowledge is moderate, suggesting that although students understand lessons in the short term, they may struggle with long-term recall and connections between topics. Despite generally positive motivation levels, students face challenges related to instructional methods. The need for more interactive and hands-on activities is the most significant concern,

indicating that traditional teaching approaches may not fully address diverse learning styles. Difficulties in understanding lessons and hesitancy in classroom participation further emphasize the importance of creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment.

Overall, the implementation of enrichment activities such as game-based learning, group work, multimedia presentations, and interactive discussions proves effective in enhancing engagement and motivation. These learner-centered strategies not only increase participation but also help address identified challenges, ultimately supporting improved academic performance in *Araling Panlipunan*.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study it concluded that students are more engaged and perform better when their efforts are recognized and lessons are linked to real-world situations. Even though visual aids and organized support help students succeed, they still need to learn how to study on their own. Students are highly motivated and engaged in classroom interactions, but their ability to retain information over time can be improved. Students in *Araling Panlipunan* face notable challenges primarily related to teaching methods and the need for more interactive learning. While they are generally motivated, their ability to understand and engage with the subject matter is hindered by the lack of hands-on or student-centered learning approaches. Addressing these instructional challenges is crucial to improving academic performance and comprehension in the subject. Enrichment activities play a vital role in boosting student engagement and motivation. The use of differentiated, interactive strategies proves effective in addressing the challenges students face in traditional learning environments. These activities not only make learning more enjoyable but also enhance comprehension and retention by catering to different learning styles.